

Application of the Plithogenic-TODIM Approach for Teaching Quality Evaluation in Vocational Colleges under the Background of New Era Education

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Abstract

The goal of vocational education reform is to improve quality, and one of its key tasks is to create a system for evaluating quality that is tailored to the requirements of contemporary vocational education. International research on models for evaluating the quality of vocational education has not yet been thoroughly examined, nevertheless. This study proposes a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methodology to evaluate the teaching quality in vocational colleges. We use the TODIM methodology under the plithogenic sets to deal with uncertainty information. The TODIM methodology is used to rank the alternatives. Ten criteria and ten alternatives are used in this study. Three experts evaluated criteria and alternatives using the plithogenic numbers. Then we used the plithogenic operator to combine these numbers. The results show the Curriculum Relevance and Industry Alignment criterion has the highest importance and Institutional Reputation and Partnerships criterion has the lowest weights. The sensitivity analysis is performed to show the different ranks of alternatives and robustness of the proposed method. The results show the proposed method is strong under different criteria weights.

Keywords: Teaching quality Evaluation; Vocational Colleges; Uncertainty; TODIM Method; MCDM.

1. Introduction

Improving quality is a major global concern for vocational education. Another crucial strategic issue for China's vocational education reform is creating a quality evaluation model and system to satisfy the development requirements of the country's contemporary system. Vocational education is becoming more and more popular worldwide, though the amounts and rates of growth vary by nation and region based on factors like economic development, labor supply and demand fluctuations, and the level of Information[1], [2].

The global vocational education market is projected to grow to 2026 under the macro backdrop of positive global vocational education development, surpassing USD 800 billion, despite the emergence of the global new crown pneumonia epidemic, political unrest in different nations, and severe natural disasters in recent years that have brought certain adverse effects on the world's economy, according to the "Global Vocational Education Industry Development Report 2022" released by Ariadne Consulting in July 2022. China's vocational education system produced 61 million highly qualified workers and technically proficient professionals for a variety of businesses between 2012 and 2022[3], [4].

Due to enrollment pressure and the negative social perception brought about by the Chinese public's lack of trust in vocational education, China's vocational education system needs to be modernized and redesigned with the goal of requiring quality improvement[5], [6]. In general, the growth of high-quality education is linked to the curriculum, professional environments, and the development of abilities. The skills developed via vocational education are given the importance of the times to contribute to industrial output and economic development as China's industrial transformation picks up speed. In contrast to conventional higher education, the quality of vocational education places more emphasis on skill competency and problem-solving abilities than it does on mastery of advanced information[7], [8].

This study integrates the plithogenic set, which was first presented by Samarandache, to solve the limitations of the conventional TODIM technique. A generalization of classical, fuzzy, and intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFS) is the neutrophilic set. To describe the ambiguous and inconsistent human information, a neutrosophic set is defined by degrees of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity. The neutrosophic theory's degrees of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity are unrelated to one another. While the traditional fuzzy set and IFS can only handle partial or incomplete information, the neutrosophic set can handle inconsistent, indeterminate, and incomplete information[9], [10].

This study ranks the alternatives using the TODIM method. Additionally, this study uses the plithogenic set aggregation operator, which considers the equidistant contradiction degree value between each criterion and the most significant criterion (dominant one), in an effort to improve aggregation accuracy [11], [12]. In 2017, Smarandache created the concept of a plithogenic set, which is derived from plithogeny and is a generalization of crisp, fuzzy, intuitionistic fuzzy, and neutrosophic sets. An application is chosen to implement the suggested plithogenic based TODIM framework [13], [14].

The following are this study's primary contributions:

- ❖ In the context of developing teaching quality, this study adds to the body of knowledge on evaluating of teaching quality by using ten criteria and alternatives to compute the criteria and ranking the alternatives.
- ❖ We applied the proposed methodology on application to validate it.
- ❖ This study uses a TODIM framework based on plithogenic to calculate the weight criteria and ranking the alternatives.
- ❖ The alternatives are ranked in order of significance in the current investigation based on the weight achieved.

2. Research Method

This section shows the plithogenic set and the proposed method under the plithogenic sets.

2.1 Plithogenic set

The creation, conception, growth, and formation of new things from fusions of contradictory and non-contradictory numerous old entities is known as lithogenic set, as defined by Smarandache. Plithogenic sets P , A , V , d , c , and p are made up of several components known as multi-dimensional characteristics.

The value of each attribute (V) has a degree of appurtenance $d x$; according to certain conditions, (v) of the element x , to the set P . The relationship between each attribute and the dominant (most significant) attribute value is presented by the contradiction (dissimilarity) degree function $c(v, D)$. The contradiction degree function is the key component that improves accuracy for the plithogenic aggregation operators (union, intersection, complement, inclusion, equality) [15], [16].

2.2 TODIM Method

This study shows the TODIM methodology steps[17] .

Build the decision matrix information.

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & \cdots & x_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \cdots & x_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Normalize the decision matrix

The decision matrix is normalized based on the beneficial and non-beneficial criteria such as:

$$t_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}}; i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

$$t_{ij} = \frac{1/x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m 1/x_{ij}}; i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

Relative weight

The relative weight is computed as:

$$w_j^- = \frac{w_j}{\max w} \quad (4)$$

The dominance degree

The dominance degree between one alternative and another is computed such as:

$$y_i = y(A_i, A_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n r_i(A_i, A_i) \quad (5)$$

Where the r can be computed such as:

$$r_i(A_i, A_i) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{u} \sqrt{\frac{(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j^-) |t_{ij} - t_{ji}|}{w_j^-}} & \text{if } (t_{ij} - t_{ji}) < 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } (t_{ij} - t_{ji}) = 0 \\ \sqrt{\frac{(w_j^-) |t_{ij} - t_{ji}|}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j^-}} & \text{if } (t_{ij} - t_{ji}) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where u refers to the attenuation factor for the losses.

The overall dominance degree

The overall dominance degree is computed such as:

$$p_i = \frac{r_i - \min r_i}{\max r_i - \min r_i} \quad (7)$$

Rank the alternatives.

The alternatives are ranked based on the highest value in p_i .

Figure 1. The roadmap of the research.

2.3 Research framework

This research can analyze the factors for evaluating the Teaching Quality Evaluation in Vocational Colleges. Figure 1 presents the brief roadmap of the present work. The step by step is developed to obtain the goals of the research work is discussed below:

- Identify the factors of Teaching Quality Evaluation in Vocational Colleges thorough set of previous studies.
- Select the best alternative based on the decision-making panel to apply the proposed TODIM methodology under uncertainty.
- Discuss the factors of the Teaching Quality Evaluation in Vocational Colleges with the decision makers and experts to obtain the highest importance.
- Conducted a decision matrix between the criteria and alternatives based on opinions of a set of experts.
- Combine the opinions of the expert's matrix using the plithogenic aggregation operator to obtain a single matrix.
- Compute the crisp values and then compute the criteria weights using the normalization of crisp values.
- Then apply the TODIM method under the plithogenic sets to rank the alternatives and select the best one.

3. Results and Discussion

The proposed plithogenic-TODIM method is applied to case study to rank a set of alternatives.

3.1 Application of plithogenic based TODIM framework

In this part, the proposed methodology is applied to compute the criteria weights and rank the alternatives. the application and the results obtained are as follows:

Stage 1: Validating of criteria and alternatives.

In this stage, the set of criteria and alternatives are identified based on previous studies analysis and opinions of three experts and decision makers. The decision makers panel was also authorized.

Then with the assistance of the decision makers panel, the ten criteria and ten alternatives are collected in this study. Then the relationship between the criteria and alternatives is built to show the importance of the criteria by the decision makers.

Stage 2: Computing the criteria weights using the plithogenic sets.

In this stage, the decision makers panel provides an evaluation of the criteria and alternatives in the decision matrix. Table 1 shows the information about the decision maker’s panel.

Table 1. Demographic profile of expert’s panel.

	<i>Positing in firms</i>	<i>Academic degree</i>	<i>Experience</i>
DM1	Senior	M.Sc.	20
DM2	Manger	Ph.D.	25
DM3	Manger	Ph.D.	30

Ten criteria and alternatives are used in this work. Tables 2-4 show the plithogenic numbers in the decision matrix. Then we used the plithogenic operator to aggregate these decision matrices. Then we convert these numbers into crips values. Then we normalize these values to compute the criteria weights. Table 5 shows the criteria weights.

Table 2. The decision matrix 1

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀				
A ₁	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.65, 0.45, 0.45)	(0.30, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.45, 0.60)	(0.30, 0.40, 0.50)	(0.80, 0.30, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.70, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.60, 0.85)	(0.70, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.85, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.40, 0.70)	(0.75, 0.60, 0.50)
A ₂	(0.50, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.80, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.60, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.50, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.70, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.85)	(0.60, 0.10, 0.80)	(0.75, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.85)	(0.60, 0.60, 0.80)
A ₃	(0.40, 0.50, 0.50)	(0.70, 0.85, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.50)	(0.75, 0.70, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.80)	(0.70, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.10, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.75, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.80)	(0.75, 0.75, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)
A ₄	(0.25, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.25, 0.80)	(0.05, 0.60, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.75, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
A ₅	(0.10, 0.85, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.10, 0.85)	(0.05, 0.75, 0.05)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
A ₆	(0.40, 0.50, 0.80)	(0.70, 0.45, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.50, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.10, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
A ₇	(0.25, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.70, 0.10, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.95, 0.05)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
A ₈	(0.10, 0.85, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.45, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.95, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
A ₉	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.50, 0.60, 0.45)	(0.40, 0.45, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
A ₁₀	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.50, 0.60)	(0.70, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)

Table 3. The decision matrix 2

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀				
A ₁	(0.50, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.30, 0.40, 0.50)	(0.80, 0.30, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.70, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.60, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)
A ₂	(0.50, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
A ₃	(0.65, 0.45, 0.45)	(0.30, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.75, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
A ₄	(0.65, 0.45, 0.45)	(0.30, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
A ₅	(0.10, 0.85, 0.85)	(0.75, 0.50, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)
A ₆	(0.25, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.60)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.40, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
A ₇	(0.50, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.60, 0.40, 0.80)
A ₈	(0.50, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.85, 0.50, 0.85)
A ₉	(0.50, 0.60, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.80, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)
A ₁₀	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.50, 0.60, 0.45)	(0.40, 0.50, 0.60)	(0.70, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)

Table 4. The decision matrix 3

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
A ₁	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)
A ₂	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
A ₃	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
A ₄	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
A ₅	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
A ₆	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)
A ₇	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
A ₈	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)
A ₉	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)
A ₁₀	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.80)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)

Table 5. Criteria weights.

Criteria	Weights
C ₁ Teaching Effectiveness	0.104738
C ₂ Resource Availability and Infrastructure	0.099943
C ₃ Teacher Qualifications and Professional Development	0.102379
C ₄ Student Engagement and Satisfaction	0.094189
C ₅ Integration of Technology in Teaching	0.099986
C ₆ Support Services and Career Guidance	0.09307
C ₇ Institutional Reputation and Partnerships	0.092526
C ₈ Student Learning Outcomes	0.100843
C ₉ Practical Training and Skill Development	0.104518
C ₁₀ Curriculum Relevance and Industry Alignment	0.107808

Stage 3: Ranking the alternatives using the TODIM method under the plithogenic numbers. We starting with a combined decision matrix to normalize the decision matrix between the criteria and alternatives as shown in Table 6. All criteria are beneficial. Then we compute the relative by dividing the criteria weights by the maximum value in criteria weights. Then we compute the dominance degree. Then we compute the overall dominance degree. Then we ranked the alternatives as shown in Figure 2.

Table 6. The normalization matrix

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
A ₁	0.105892	0.080366	0.088016	0.108566	0.125262	0.159334	0.086808	0.089356	0.082965	0.057619
A ₂	0.105892	0.08282	0.139967	0.109669	0.087904	0.084197	0.138315	0.042588	0.086214	0.119232
A ₃	0.106054	0.122713	0.084698	0.095669	0.136423	0.056777	0.08887	0.100739	0.070835	0.083584
A ₄	0.070687	0.105585	0.088016	0.06595	0.112303	0.059036	0.114048	0.11335	0.097197	0.042061
A ₅	0.031266	0.112352	0.088328	0.135872	0.071938	0.153382	0.141203	0.111349	0.122444	0.112393
A ₆	0.086033	0.107249	0.103072	0.159614	0.135993	0.077284	0.105929	0.08154	0.070835	0.13113
A ₇	0.105148	0.115031	0.106697	0.087301	0.150361	0.138113	0.138925	0.08154	0.133149	0.057619

A_8	0.098509	0.090162	0.112293	0.085275	0.045351	0.146099	0.059383	0.120156	0.107433	0.129087
A_9	0.141059	0.103356	0.088016	0.076365	0.072338	0.059036	0.059383	0.120156	0.098831	0.137042
A_{10}	0.149462	0.080366	0.100896	0.075718	0.062127	0.066743	0.067136	0.139226	0.130096	0.130232

Figure 2. The rank of alternatives.

4. Analysis

In this work, sensitivity analysis of the criteria weights and ranking of alternatives has been performed. There are two reasons to perform this analysis. In the first reason, to show the robust of the ranking of this study. In the second reason, to show the ranking of alternative is sensitive to the criteria weights. The sensitivity analysis is performed by two ways. In the first way, we can change the weights of decision makers and experts. In the second way, we can change the criteria weights.

In this work, we change the criteria weights to show the sensitivity analysis tasks. We change the criteria weights by increasing 5% and decreasing 5% as shown in Table 7. Then we apply the proposed methodology under these changes. We show the rank of alternatives is robust as shown in Table 8.

Table 7. Change in the weights to show ranks.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Case 8	Case 9	Case 10
C ₁	0.154738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738	0.104738
C ₂	0.049943	0.149943	0.099943	0.099943	0.099943	0.099943	0.099943	0.099943	0.099943	0.099943
C ₃	0.102379	0.052379	0.152379	0.102379	0.102379	0.102379	0.102379	0.102379	0.102379	0.102379
C ₄	0.094189	0.094189	0.044189	0.144189	0.094189	0.094189	0.094189	0.094189	0.094189	0.094189
C ₅	0.099986	0.099986	0.099986	0.049986	0.149986	0.099986	0.099986	0.099986	0.099986	0.099986
C ₆	0.09307	0.09307	0.09307	0.09307	0.04307	0.14307	0.09307	0.09307	0.09307	0.09307
C ₇	0.092526	0.092526	0.092526	0.092526	0.092526	0.042526	0.142526	0.092526	0.092526	0.092526
C ₈	0.100843	0.100843	0.100843	0.100843	0.100843	0.100843	0.050843	0.150843	0.100843	0.100843
C ₉	0.104518	0.104518	0.104518	0.104518	0.104518	0.104518	0.104518	0.054518	0.154518	0.054518
C ₁₀	0.107808	0.107808	0.107808	0.107808	0.107808	0.107808	0.107808	0.107808	0.057808	0.157808

Table 8. Rank of alternatives from increasing weights by 5%.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Case 8	Case 9	Case 10
A ₁	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
A ₂	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
A ₃	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
A ₄	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	4
A ₅	6	6	6	7	5	6	6	6	5	6
A ₆	5	5	5	5	6	5	5	5	7	5
A ₇	7	7	7	6	7	7	7	7	6	7
A ₈	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
A ₉	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
A ₁₀	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	3

5. Conclusions

This study proposed a MCDM methodology to rank the alternatives of teaching quality of vocational colleges. The plithogenic sets are used in this study to deal with the uncertainty data. Three experts evaluated the criteria and then we use the plithogenic numbers to evaluate the criteria and alternatives. Then we used the plithogenic operators to combine these numbers. Then we obtained the crisp values. We validated the proposed methodology through an application with ten criteria and ten alternatives. The criteria weights are computed using the normalized values. Then we applied the TODIM methodology to rank the alternatives. The results show alternative 2 has the highest rank and alternative 9 has the lowest rank. We performed a sensitivity analysis to show the different rank of alternatives. The results show our methodology has a stable different rank of alternatives under ten cases in change of criteria weights.

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